

ISic1558

I.Sicily inscription 1558

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

2015.07.23 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Kakylon

Place of origin (modern)

Monte Saraceno

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Ravanusa, Museo Archeologico

Salvatore Lauricella

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Φαγιάδα ἐμί

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493904

EDCS 41300033

PHI 175631

PHI 330041

Bibliography

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